

Conference Abstract

An integrative approach to species delimitation of Antarctic benthic amphipods

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Abstract

The Antarctic Peninsula, particularly its northern part, is one of the regions that has experienced significant warming over the past 50 years, at a rate higher than the global average (Kim et al. 2014; Carrasco et al. 2021). The rise in atmospheric temperature and sea surface temperature affects cryospheric processes and the ecosystems in this region (Convey and Peck 2019). Amphipod crustaceans are one of the most speciose and dominant groups in the sublittoral zone of the Southern Ocean, with a high diversity in life styles, trophic types and habitats (Broyer et al. 2008). They constitute a significant trophic resource for a number of Southern Ocean fishes, invertebrates, seabirds and mammals and play a key role in coastal Antarctic ecosystems in terms of carbon flow, nutrient storage, and nutrient cycling (Jażdżewska 2011; Jażdżewska and Siciński 2017; Revanales et al. 2024).

The integrative approach to studying benthic Antarctic amphipods is a multi-component strategy that combines morphological analysis, molecular and genetic methods, ecological and biogeographical data, and behavioral and functional traits to obtain a more complete and reliable picture of their taxonomy, ecology, and evolution. The taxonomic composition of benthic amphipods from Maritime Antarctica was studied during the austral summers of 2019/20 and 2022/23, within the frameworks of the XXVIII and XXXI Bulgarian Antarctic Expeditions and the IV Turkish Antarctic Expedition. A total of 27 localities were surveyed: 15 along the coastline of the South Bay (Livingston Island) and 12 along the coastline of the Marguerite Bay (Horseshoe and Dismal Islands). For

the purpose of this research, two mitochondrial (*cox 1* and 16S rDNA) and two nuclear (Histone 3 and 28S rDNA) regions were sequenced for representative specimens.

Within the integrative taxonomy we applied, a total of 38 amphipod species, belonging to 23 families were revealed (Fig. 1). Species relationships were assessed on individual gene-based phylogenetic hypotheses. Biogeographic and phylogenetic relationships were explored based on the multilocus phylogeny (*cox1*+16S+28S+H3). Our analyses revealed higher than previously thought diversity with evidence of several species-complexes.

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An Integrative Approach to Species Delimitation of Antarctic Benthic Amphipods

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Introduction
Amphipod crustaceans are one of the most species-rich group in the Antarctic waters having a high diversity of life styles, trophic types and preferred habitats. In the South Ocean they are an important element of benthic ecosystems, and many species are endemic for the Antarctic region. The taxonomic composition of Antarctic benthic amphipods was studied during the austral summers of 2019/20 and 2022/23, within the frameworks of the XXVIII and XXXI Bulgarian Antarctic Expeditions (BAE) and the IV Turkish Antarctic Expedition.

Results
A total of 38 amphipod species, belonging to 23 families were revealed. Species relationships were assessed on individual gene-based phylogenetic hypotheses. Our analyses revealed higher than previously thought diversity with evidence of several species-complexes. Biogeographic and phylogenetic relationships will be explored based on the multilocus phylogeny (*cox1*+16S+28S+H3).

Materials and methods
Sampling was carried out in the shallow littoral zone (0-2 m) using a hand netting or a Raushert dredge in the sublittoral zone (5-40 m). In an integrative taxonomy framework we used, combining morphological, molecular and ecological data. For this purpose, two mitochondrial (*cox1* and 16S rDNA) and two nuclear (Histone 3 and 28S rDNA) regions were sequenced for representative specimens.

A total of 27 localities were surveyed: 15 in South Bay, Livingston Island and 12 localities in Marguerite Bay Horseshoe and Dismal Islands.

Charcotia sbera Chevreux, 1906
Fam. Lysianassoidea

Chiroedon femoratus (Piffier, 1888)
Fam. Tryphosidae

Paradesmone fasticaula Chevreux, 1906
Fam. Dexaminidae

Conclusions
This study highlights the importance of integrating multiple lines of evidence to address the significant knowledge gap in Antarctic amphipod diversity. Despite the increasing research efforts in recent years, over 90% of the Antarctic amphipod species remain unsequenced with most existing data originating from a single biogeographical region. Therefore, expanding morphological and genetic datasets across different regions is crucial for advancing our understanding of the evolutionary history and ecological roles of benthic amphipods in Southern Ocean ecosystems.

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Figure 1. [doi](#)

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Despite the increasing research efforts in recent years, only 10% of known Antarctic amphipod species are represented by barcodes (Grant and Linse 2009; Jażdżewska et al. 2021). This study highlights the importance of integrating multiple lines of evidence to address the significant knowledge gap in Antarctic amphipod diversity. Expanding morphological and genetic datasets across different regions is crucial for advancing our understanding of the evolutionary history and ecological roles of benthic amphipods in Southern Ocean ecosystems.

Keywords

Amphipoda, taxonomy, barcoding, South Shetland Archipelago, Antarctic Peninsula

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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